

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ABANAS****FIRST NAME: Dieudonné Adozong****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: (MS Word 2016 on Windows 10)

List your 5-7 key concepts with the page number in:

1. Essay Writing (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 6-14)
2. Punctuation (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 15-23)
3. American Vs. British English (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 33-39)
5. Style guide (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 40-42)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The ACA-401/ACA-401D syllabus, revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma, and the introductory videos provide an overview of the essential principles of document writing. Using these resources enables students to familiarize themselves with the tools offered by Euclid University. The course content provides the necessary tips and rules for successful document writing.

This first course, consisting of eight (8) chapters, covered essential elements such as essay writing, correct punctuation, plagiarism, and applying conventional style. It sheds light on the existing differences between American and British English and guides the student in choosing to ensure coherence in the document (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 3).

This program establishes a solid foundation for students' long-term academic and professional development while giving them an insight into the approaches, requirements, and methods involved.

The concepts covered are timely and relevant to anyone enrolled in a Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) program. I noted that to write a good document, you need to have a solid grounding in punctuation and spelling.

Our discussion will focus on five concepts from the ACA-401D syllabus that are available to us. These concepts include essay writing, punctuation, American and British English use, plagiarism, and the style guide.

2) ESSAY WRITING

The first chapter of the ACA-401D syllabus for the first period covers the fundamentals of essay writing. It details the essential preparatory steps and offers practical advice on how to write an effective essay. It also covers formulating an appropriate introduction, body, and conclusion (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 10).

Starting as early as possible in this type of essay is advisable by drawing up a structured work plan (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 8). This plan enables students to demonstrate their understanding of a subject, organize their ideas, analyze information, and develop personal reflection (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 9.). This type of writing is based on solid research, relevant quotations, and references to previous work based on evidence and facts in response to hypotheses (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 7). I share this point of view, as its arguments correspond to my daily practices. To ensure the successful implementation of humanitarian projects, I prepared a detailed work plan, highlighting clear project objectives. Since these projects are limited, I start their implementation as soon as possible and ensure that they do not postpone planned activities.

When writing an essay, rereading the draft several times is essential. Setting the document aside for a while or submitting it to others for reading is often advisable. This practice allows for generating new creative ideas and editing the essay (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 11). I approve of this method, as proofreading helps to spot spelling mistakes and refine the essay. Based on my experience monitoring construction sites, I am used to calling in people from outside the team. Although they are not engineers, they often manage to spot minor errors that I missed during my checks.

This first-period chapter gave me an overview of the essential elements for successful essay writing. An academic essay must organize ideas logically and coherently while adhering to academic standards such as rigorous sourcing, objectivity, and clarity of expression.

3) PUNCTUATION

The second chapter deals with specific rules concerning punctuation, presenting guidelines and principles for its use within a sentence. Generally, it is advisable to use punctuation sparingly while preserving the sentence's meaning (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 16). I noticed that punctuation plays a crucial role in the writing of an academic

essay. It helps to organize ideas, clarify the meaning of sentences, and improve the readability of the text. It is essential not to overload the text with excessive punctuation, which can detract from clarity. However, contrary to my view that punctuation can be placed however you like, I learned that it is crucial to know about punctuation marks and their usage to distinguish between correct and incorrect punctuation. For example, the erroneous use of commas or periods can alter the relationship between propositions in the sentence. This can distort subtle meanings and even lead to misunderstandings.

4) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

This course explores the similarities and differences between American and British English. American English predominates in the world due to factors such as population size, the wealth and influence of the American economy, and the political and economic position of the United States of America (USA) on the international stage, among others (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 25). I confirm this observation because in my French-speaking country, teaching English at school mainly follows the American model.

There are significant divergences between American and British English, linked to their distinct national histories and cultural developments and the way the two variants have evolved as a result (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 25). As a French speaker, I learned through this course that there are significant differences, particularly in punctuation and other aspects (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 25-32). It is, therefore, crucial to be familiar with them. When writing documents, it is essential to choose the appropriate language variant to ensure consistency, facilitate reading, and improve comprehension for readers.

5) PLAGIARISM

In this chapter, the authors address the issue of plagiarism in all its forms. Plagiarism occurs when an author uses a source of information without attributing authorship to its true author (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 34). Plagiarism has long been viewed with concern by the academic community as a serious, reprehensible act threatening fundamental academic values (Pecorari 2008). It is crucial always to acknowledge the source of information, as failure to do so can have consequences for the author and the quality of the article. I learned that to avoid plagiarism, you must correctly cite the author or source of information used (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 34). I believe that to enhance the value of the article and for the sake of intellectual honesty, it is essential that all sources of information mentioned in the article are correctly attributed to their author.

I observed that an author could cite other information sources when quoting, paraphrasing, or mentioning phrases and statistical data borrowed from another source (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 35, 36, 38).

6) STYLE GUIDE

In this chapter, the authors discuss style guide rules and standards to ensure consistency in writing, particularly for a given project or organization. A style guide is a way of documenting your approach, as a writer, to some aspects of writing style that need to be consistent (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 41). I understood that a style guide is essential for a writer, as it helps ensure that the article is clear and consistent. This uniformity provides proofreaders and readers with clear reference points for stylistic choices. What's more, I found that, in one article, several authors can contribute so that the style aligns with that of the concerned publication, company, or website. I found this particularly important because, in my experience, any customization or modification of the style of a document to suit personal preferences, particularly in the context of a project for a funding agency, can result in your work being rejected.

Style is not just the correct use of punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary but encompasses many different aspects. It is an invaluable tool for any copywriter, especially for freelance writers (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 42). I stress the importance of style when writing a development or humanitarian project. To ensure validation or funding of the project, it is essential to follow the guidelines provided in the document to the letter, particularly about writing style.

After reviewing the course, I found that other internationally recognized rules could also be applied. However, EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian) style. For me, this is a new learning opportunity. This is the first time I used this tool since the start of my academic career, and it will be helpful for my future studies and professional job. I recommend this style to anyone pursuing scholarly research, as I find it simple and practical.

7) CONCLUSION

By reviewing this course, I deepened my understanding of International Academic Writing. Key concepts such as essay writing, plagiarism, punctuation, and style guide gave me a new perspective on the methods and rules of writing a scientific paper. It was a rich experience learning and discovering new working tools from this course and the guidance delivered through videos. I particularly appreciate the response paper, as it opens up new avenues for my academic and professional development. The skills acquired here will help me realize my dream of obtaining a Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) in Climate Change and Sustainability at Euclid University.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Pecorari, Diane. 2008. *Academic Writing and Plagiarism: A Linguistic Analysis*. United Kingdom: [Continuum International Publishing Group Ltd.](#)

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.